

INVESTIGATION OF THE PROPERTIES OF COMPOSITE MATERIALS BASED ON CEMENTS CONTAINING MICRO-AND NANOPARTICLES FROM RED MUD

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ABSTRACT

In the construction industry, the problems of material consumption, high production costs and poor quality are particularly acute. With increasing requirements to the quality of construction there is a need in the construction materials produced with relatively low cost in quality and durability that exceeds existing analogues. The main prerequisites for the synthesis of strength and durability of high-quality concretes and other cement composites is the more complete use of the latent energy of cement. In recent years, this is usually achieved through the use of active mineral additives introduced into the cementing composition at the stage of preparation of cements with reactive mineral additives which links "ballast" hydrolytic lime to cementing calcium hydrosilicates which is used for obtaining concretes and other composite materials or as an add-on component in the concrete mix. In this regard, the development of highly active mineral additives that increase the efficiency of the use of cement allows to produce concretes and other cement composites with higher physical and mechanical properties is an important scientific and applied task.

Keywords: Aluminate Cements, Red Mud, Waste Products, Strength of Cement Compositions.

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1. INTRODUCTION

Lately there is an urgent need for speedy development of high-strength heat-resistant concrete technology based on local raw materials using nano-additives. The obtained materials based on aluminate cements can be used in structures operating at high temperatures, high static and dynamic loads, thermal units, and building structures exposed to prolonged heat, for

foundations and air heaters industrial furnaces, enterprises of the chemical industry, for firing in the production of construction materials, in oil refineries [1], [2].

In practice, in order to obtain construction with the required operational strength, the reduction in strength, which is observed during the first commissioning of the construction, is compensated by the overrun of the binder [3]. One of the ways to eliminate this disadvantage is to develop composite binders based on aluminate cements and dispersed additives.

The development of new heat-resistant composites based on aluminate cements is relevant [4] and will allow the use aluminate and aluminous cements as a basis for composite materials operating over a wide range of temperatures, which in turn will be directed to design compositions of composite astringents that ensure the intensification of these processes and increase the strength of cement stone [5].

The purpose of this article is to justify the hardening of cement compositions with additives in compositions based on aluminate cements which contain micro- and nano dispersions of red mud.

Secondary raw materials of non-ferrous metallurgy is a large reserve for the production of building materials [6]. Slimes are the main technogenic product of the aluminum industry, the number of which in dumps is estimated at tens of millions of tons [7].

Red mud can be processed into alumina, alkali, cast iron and cement by re-firing a mixture of sludge with coal and limestone in a rotary kiln at a temperature of 300-1000 ° C, followed by a smelting of partially reduced clinker in an electric arc furnace [8]. As a result, cast iron and self-dissolving aluminum-calcium slag are obtained by leaching which converts the alumina into a solution, and then into hydroxide and alumina [9]. Sludge after leaching is used for the production of cement [10]. One of the main ways of recycling red mud in the field of construction production is to use it as an iron-alumina component of the raw mix in the manufacture of Portland cement clinker [11].

2. MATERIAL AND METHODS

On the basis of a generalization of literary-scientific material, it can be concluded that the red mud of separate plants was investigated as an additive, which will increase the mechanical strength of concrete [7], [12].

The use of aluminous slurries will allow to expand the range of concretes, practically not changing existing technologies for manufacturing of small wall materials [5], and will also contribute to ecological improvement of the environment through utilization of harmful substances contained in technogenic products [13].

Red mud is characterized by a constant chemical composition. According to the laboratory data, the amount of oxides in the composition of red mud varies in such limits (mass%) see Table 1 below.

Table 1 Content of oxides in the composition of red slime

Element	Fe	FeO	Fe ₂ O ₃	Al ₂ O ₃	SiO ₂	CaO	MgO	TiO ₂	SO ₃	P ₂ O ₅	K ₂ O	Na ₂ OH	Other
Mass fraction, %	33,3	5,25	41,8	13,5	9,79	8,77	0,96	4,78	2,125	0,94	0,21	4,08	1,79

Portland cement and aluminous cements were used as raw materials. The table below show the characteristics of used cements.

Table 2 Chemical compositions of cements

Cement	Chemical composition, mass %							
	SiO ₂	Al ₂ O ₃	Fe ₂ O ₃	CaO	MgO	SO ₃	other	amount
Portland cement	20,44	4,84	3,65	62,4	2,7	2,77	1,34	98,14
Alumina cement	12,95	45,12	3,44	40,02	1,12	2,43	1,4	98,62

The criterion for assessing the effectiveness of the method of introducing additives into cement was the activity of the sample beams of cement 40mm x 40mm x 160mm after 28 days. The results of the studies are presented in Table 3.

Table 3 Influence of the method of introducing additives on the activity of cement

Cement	Additive	Quantity of additive, % to dry cement	Method of introducing the additive	Activity after 28 days of hardening	
				MPa	kN
Aluminous	Red mud	1	With mixing water	87,88	219,7
Aluminous	Red mud	3	With mixing water	74,9	190,4
Aluminous	Red mud	5	With mixing water	76,56	190,9
Aluminous	Red mud	7	With mixing water	72,78	183,4
Aluminous	Red mud	1	In cement	82,88	201,8
Aluminous	Red mud	3	In cement	78,84	191,4
Aluminous	Red mud	5	In cement	80,56	197,4
Aluminous	Red mud	7	In cement	74,78	189,4

As shown by the conducted studies, the most effective way of introducing red mud, at which the cement activity after 28 days of hardening is maximum, is the introduction of an additive with mixing water. Probably, when water is mixed, the surface properties of the particles change, which contributes to their adhesion on cement particles. This effect can be enhanced by hydration of cement. This is due to the fact that the introduction of additives into the mixing water promotes a more even distribution of the additive in the volume.

3. RESULTS

The granulometric composition of the sludge is characterized by a large content of the huge fractions - particles > 58 μm in size in all samples of sludge more than 92,5 %; The fractional ranges are as follows, %: < 20 μm 2,1-27,7; 20-67 μm 2,6-19,9; 67-125 μm 9,3-26,6; 125-400 μm 11,4-31,4; 400-500 μm 2,5-7,2; > 500 microns 2,7-8,3.

The density of this sludge is 3.00-3.16 g/cm³.

The specific surface of highly disperse sludges is 10-20 m²/g, and the specific surface value is correlated with the content of tiny particles.

The Figure 1 shows the microstructure of the red sludge.

Figure 1 Microstructure of the red sludge

Table 4 Element composition of red sludge

Element	AN	Series	Net	unn. [wt. %]	C norm. [wt. %]	C Atom. [at. %]	C Error [%]
Oxygen	8	K-series	4890	36.49	35.24	50.96	4.7
Carbon	6	K-series	866	9.09	8.77	16.90	1.6
Calcium	20	K-series	10523	20.31	19.61	11.32	0.6
Iron	26	K-series	4948	21.69	20.94	8.68	0.7
Silicon	14	K-series	6084	10.50	10.14	8.35	0.5
Aluminium	13	K-series	814	1.61	1.55	1.33	0.1
Sodium	11	K-series	332	1.28	1.23	1.24	0.1

According to the data in the tables and figures, one can observe the characteristics of the sludges. Content of basic oxides,% (by weight): CaO 40-45; SiO₂ 15-20; Fe₂O₃ 20-25. The main phases: dicalcium silicate, magnesite, perovskite. Dispersion of the fraction > 53 μm 90%, S = 20-60 m²/g.

The main feature of the sludge characteristic is high content of dicalcium silicate and a Fe₂O₃ (20-25%). Such slurries are characterized by a calcium-silicate composition and a larger particle size than Bayer's, and also by a large specific surface. The presence of significant amounts of hydraulically active dicalcium silicate in the sludge predetermines the expediency of its use both as an independent binder and as a component of building binders. It should be emphasized that careful mixing of components is one of the most important conditions for the successful implementation of any cement technology. Good mixing of cement particles with water promotes a more complete and rapid physical and chemical interaction, as well as a uniform coating of the aggregate grains with a thin layer of cement paste.

Experiments [8], [14] to study the properties of cement and solidified composites have shown that cement with recommended additives, in contrast to cements without these additives, has a higher strength and heat resistance. The recommended time for cement grinding is 2-5 minutes. An increase in the specific surface area of cements above the optimal level may lead to aggregation of the part, and to an increase in water retention in cement pastes and suspensions.

Figure 2 Red sludge chemical composition

Figure 3 Microphotograph of red sludge

This phenomenon, in turn, has an undesirable effect on the strength properties of solidified cement, and also adversely affects the frost resistance of materials [9]. The data obtained after 5 minutes of grinding and the study of the properties of cement attest to the sufficient subtlety of grinding of the cement particles.

The results of the experiments showed the positive effect of red sludge on the strength properties of Portland and aluminate cements. The recommended number of microspheres is 2-5% of the weight of the cement. In the cases of aluminous and expanding cements, due to the presence of rapidly hydrating aluminate phases, it is necessary to use the optimum amount of superplasticizer. In order to increase the plasticity and workability of cement, it is recommended to use a superplasticizer in an amount of up to 0.2% of the weight of the cement.

It is important to determine the effect of modifying additives on the timing of setting the cement. The results of the study of the effect of additives on the setting time of cement are given in the table below.

Table 5 Timing of setting the cement

Type of binder	Beginning of setting, hour :minute	End of setting, hour :minute
Portland Cement M500	2:40	4:00
Portland cement with red sludge additive 1 %	1:55	3:45
Portland cement with red sludge additive 3 %	1:35	3:25
Portland cement with red sludge additive 5 %	1:15	3:10
Aluminous cement	2:30	3:45
Aluminous cement with red sludge additive 1 %	2:00	3:20
Aluminous cement with red sludge additive 3 %	1:35	3:00
Aluminous cement with red sludge additive 5 %	1:10	2:20

For tested compositions and astringents, a significant reduction in the setting time is observed. This is due to the fact that additives bind low-basic calcium hydrosilicates, formed during the hardening of cement, calcium hydroxide, which leads to an acceleration of structure formation processes.

Studies aimed at determining the normal density of cement paste, which contains an active mineral additive based on red sludge, are of considerable interest.

The results of the studies are given in the table below.

Table 6 Results of the determination of the cement test's normal density

Name of indicator	Cement without additive	Cement wit red sludge additive 2 %	Cement wit red sludge additive 3 %	Cement wit red sludge additive 5 %
PC (portland cement) 400				
Specific surface area – 2880 g/cm ²				
Normal density, %	26	24	23	23
AC (aluminous cement)				
Specific surface area – g/cm ²				
Normal density, %	25	24	24	23

As can be seen from the Table 6, the normal density of the cement paste without additives is 26% for PCs and 25% for AC. For the cement test containing nano-additives, the normal density of the binder is slightly lower and is 24, 23 and 23% for the PCs, and 24, 24 and 23% for AC respectively. The reduction in the water demand of cement with these additives is due to the fact that when adding micro- and nanodispersions, it decreases Porosity and silica content is increased.

In the technological process, an important operation is the method of introducing the additive into the cement.

In practice, cement additives are introduced in several ways [9], [4]. The most traditional method is when additives in cement are introduced with mixing water, while thoroughly mixing the cement paste (separate method of preparation).

Another way of introducing the additive is to co-milling the cement and the additive. For disperse systems prone to aggregation of particles when water is added, the additive is introduced together with the plasticizer.

The criterion for evaluating the effectiveness of the method of introducing an additive into cement is the strength of a cement stone for compression.

Table 7 Physical and mechanical properties of alumina cement with micro and nano additives

Additive index	Quantity of additive, % of dry cement	Activity					
		3 days		7 days		28 days,	
		MPa	κH	MPa	κH	MPa	κH
Cement with the addition of red sludge	1	52,6	131,7	63,65	159,1	87,88	219,7
	2	54,4	132,6	64,56	160,5	88,02	220,0
	3	56,4	130,3	65,4	162,3	74,9	190,4
	5	62,1	134,5	67,2	168,3	76,56	190,9

The results of experiments with concrete compositions based on alumina cement also indicate the positive effect of the above additives. Table 8 shows the compositions of cements and additives for heat-resistant concrete.

Table 8 Compositions of cements and additives for (per 1 m³ of solution)

Cement	W/C	Additive	Quantity of additive, % by weight of dry cement
Aluminous	0,26	Red mud	2

Studies have shown that adding red mud to cement leads to more intensive hydration of cement, increasing the density of cement stone. These factors contributed to an increase in frost resistance of cement stone with an additive

Thus, the use of red mud reduces the water-cement ratio, the workability of the mixture. Investigation of the physical and mechanical properties of cement samples showed that at the age of 3 days the samples made using red mud had a strength exceeding the strength of samples of ordinary water by 4.5%. Red mud has a plasticizing effect on cement pastes, contributing to the formation of a structure with a lower porosity, which affects the strength properties and frost resistance of the samples.

The choice of concrete mixes with the addition of red mud is aimed at determining such a component ratio, including red mud, in which the required properties of the concrete mixture and concrete are achieved with a minimum cement consumption. In a concrete mix, red mud serves not only an active mineral additive, which increases the amount of binder, but also as a microfiller, which improves granulometry of sand and actively influences the processes of structure formation of concrete. Given the polyfunctional nature of the additive, introducing it only to replace part of the cement or part of the sand does not allow to solve the problem of optimizing the formulations.

Figure 4 Kinetics of a set of strength of concrete with red mud

The Figure 4 shows the kinetics of the strength of concrete with red sludge.

It can be seen from the figure that Portland cement has an intensive growth in strength during the initial hardening period, then experienced the attenuation of the strength and the yield to a stabilized strength value. The strength of this binder increases for 28 days.

Dependencies of the strength change during the compression of concrete from the level of microdoses of red sludge from the consumption of cement are shown in the figure below.

The nature of the curves in Figure 5 shows that the introduction of additives into the composition of concrete on the basis of red sludge helps to increase the strength of concrete in comparison with the base composition without the additive. In this case, there is a clear picture of a significant increase in the strength of concrete, especially in the early stages of hardening.

Comparison of the microstructure of the cement stone of the control sample (without addition) with the test samples with the additive shows some difference. The microstructure of a cement stone without an additive is characterized by a greater porosity than the microstructure of the test samples.

To achieve high strength concrete containing red mud, the chemical-mineralogical composition of the clinker is of particular importance.

Figure 5 Change in strength of concrete

The strength of concrete based on red mud steamed at 95° C is 12-15% higher than the strength of concrete steamed at 80° C. Increasing the temperature, allows for 1-2 hours to reduce the time of heat treatment.

4. CONCLUSION

The analysis carried out on the use of additives for the modification of mineral binders showed the following:

- The physical and mechanical properties of building composites based on mineral binders are determined primarily by their structure. In some cases, dispersed substances which are often inert with respect to the liquid phase, are additionally introduced into the composition of mineral binders. These additives improve the structure of the composite, resulting in increased physical and mechanical properties of composites on mineral binders.
- Based on the above views on the relationship between physical and mechanical properties and the structure of building composites, the directional regulation of the structure of cement composites by introducing a highly active mineral additive is promising.

The most important indicators of the operational properties of concrete are the kinetic characteristics of their variation over time. For concretes hardening for a long time under air-humid conditions, one of such characteristics is the strength and kinetics of its variation with time. Comparative studies of the strength of portland cement with additives based on red mud were carried out.

- It was found out that active mineral additives slightly reduced the time of setting portland cement;
- It has been established that mineral additives positively influence the uniformity of the change in the volume of cement stone;
- It was revealed that the cement stone on portland cement with mineral additives intensifies faster than the samples without additives.

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